

LINGUISTIC NATURE OF ENGLISH METAPHORS

Akhmedova Nigina Ikhtiyorovna,

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service.

Teacher of the department of "Teaching languages".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7957027>

Abstract: The aim of this article is to explore conceptual metaphor used in modern internet discourse in the English language, proceeding from the cognitive point of view and to identify the main features internet discourse of conceptual metaphor.

Key words: Metaphor, comparison, figurative sense, phenomena, syntactic semantics, semblance of shape, color affinity.

Nowadays it obvious that in contemporary linguistics the concept of metaphor is used in any field of human activity from the very beginning of the existence of mankind. In more ancient language works, one can speak of a continuous metaphorization of language. Metaphor is the transfer of a name from one object or phenomenon of reality to another based on their similarity in any respect or in contrast. Metaphor is one of the most common artistic tropes in literature. [6,5] It arises from comparison, juxtaposition of a new object with an already known one and highlighting their common features. For a metaphor to appear, you need to find points of contact between two objects or phenomena in something, for example:

- the lake is like a mirror - the mirror of the lake;
- hands like gold - hands of gold;
- hair like silver - silver hair.[2,154]

That is why the metaphor is considered a hidden comparison, in which both permanent and temporary, transitory, random similarities of objects are displayed. But unlike comparison, metaphor expresses the established similarities of objects. For example, the metaphorical connection between the meanings of the noun "nose" is based on the similarity of objects in shape and location in space: part of a person's face, an animal's muzzle;

- bird beak;
- protruding part of a teapot, jug;
- the front of the foot, shoes and stocking;
- the front of a sea vessel, airplane, etc. [1,99]

On the basis of external similarity, the sewing and surgical needle, a leaf of a coniferous tree (pine, spruce, cedar needle) and the needle of some animals (hedgehog, porcupine) received the same names. The animal-human relationship is metaphorical, and hence the names of people in a figurative sense: ram, donkey, pig, fox, magpie, wolf, bear, rooster, ox. The commonality of the feature makes it possible to transfer such a feature of a person to an object:

- the silent woman is the silent street;
- a delicate person is a delicate matter;
- a lively boy - a lively argument;
- wise old man - wise decision;
- a curious neighbor - a curious question.

The transfer of the meaning of one word to another, that is, the emergence of a metaphor, is associated with their similarity:

- semblance of shape: a lady's hat - a nail head, a head of hay - a head of hair;

- color affinity: amber beads - amber shine; golden ring - golden foliage;
- commonality of function: wipers cleared the snow - car wipers; the candle is on - the light is on; watchman (guard) - a watchman (a kitchen device that prevents milk from burning);
- similarity in arrangement: the sole of the shoe is the sole of the mountain.[3,13]

Actually two aspects of understanding metaphor are not the only ones. The understanding of this term varies from scientist to scientist. Among all the studies of metaphor, according to O. A. Rykov, three key concepts can be distinguished:

- 1) metaphor as a way of existence of the meaning of the word;
- 2) metaphor as a phenomenon of syntactic semantics;
- 3) metaphor as a way of representing meaning in a communicative act [5, 109].

The definition of the term "metaphor" is also not unambiguous. Thus, I. R. Halperin considers metaphor very broadly, defining it as "the relation of the subject-logical meaning and the contextual meaning, based on the similarity of the features of the two concepts" . The metaphor is considered by many to be the most important trope and is so characteristic of poetic language that the word itself is sometimes used as a synonym for the figurativeness of speech, as an indication that words act here not in a direct, but in a figurative sense. [4,35]

Metaphorization of meaning can be accompanied by the transition of a noun from a noun position to a predicate one. A metaphor of this type aims at individualizing an object. The figurative metaphor introduces synonyms into the language "shy" and "hare"., Davidson has nothing against the very effects of these effects produced by metaphor, he only against the associated views on how the metaphor produces this effect.

References:

1. Turner M., Fauconnier G. A. Mechanism of Creativity -Poetics today. – Vol., 1999. – 99p.
2. Цинковская Ю.В. Виды художественных метафор в современной русской прозе - Ученые записки Забайкальского государственного университета., 2010. -154.
3. Шарикова Л.А. Основы теории дискурса: словарный дискурс., Л.А. Шарикова - Альманах современной науки и образования., 2008. -13 p.
4. Юрина Е.А. Пищевая метафора -объем и границы понятия- Вестник Кемеровского государственного университета., 2015. -35p.
5. Gee J. P. An introduction to discourse analysis. Theory and practice., 2005. -109p.
6. Z.Harris "Discourse Analysis", 1952. -5p.